

Usability Evaluation Process for Domain-Specific Languages
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Usa-DSL Process Survey Guidelines

Brief Description about Usa-DSL Process

Usa-DSL process is a usability evaluation process for domain-specific languages (DSLs) that, over time, is expected to cover a broad set of needs of DSL developers with regard to evaluation of DSLs.

Usa-DSL process searches through its concepts to assist in the evaluation of the quality of the DSLs that will be delivered and used by end-users.

Usa-DSL process is characterized by four mutually supporting fundamental principles:

- Assist in the construction of the usability evaluation in a practical and efficient way;
- Assist in the DSL development through continuous feedback, promoting to continuous improvement of the language;
- Focus on the user-centered evaluation through all the construction phases, minimizing the DSL's rework and disuse;
- Make DSLs evaluation easier and productive, aiming to reach usability criteria and usage satisfaction.

The main purpose of the Usa-DSL process is to guide the questions "Who will do what, when and how?". Always iteratively and guided to the development of formal usability evaluations with ease and speed.

The main objective is to provide the procedures to perform the evaluation regarding the usability of DSLs, verifying through methods, techniques and activities how these languages meet the quality of use issues.

The Usa-DSL process deals with the elaboration of usability evaluations involving the methods Heuristic Evaluation and Usability Testing, with the intention of systematizing and developing the evaluations in a productive way and with less cost.

In order to complete this Survey you will need to perform a few steps to understand the Usa-DSL process to evaluate the usability of a DSL.

To access the Usa-DSL process, please click the link:
<http://www.lesse.com.br/usa-dsl/>

Follow the steps below for information about the Usa-DSL process:

1. Consult the "Usa-DSL Introduction" in the top left part and browse this page for process information;
2. Consult "Getting Started":
 - Explore the Usa-DSL Process roadmap. If you want to know the origin of the Process, please see the Usa-DSL Framework;
3. In "Steps Usa-DSL" analyze the information of each Step and its images to understand how Profiles and Activities are allocated;
4. In "Phases" analyze the information about each Usa-DSL phase;
5. Check the "Activities" that are part of the process;
6. Consult the "Profiles" that are part of this process and what they are responsible for;
7. Identify the "Work Products" that are part of each Task;
8. Finally, go through the "Usa-DSL Life Cycle" and check how is the flow of each usability assessment that is addressed by the process:
 - Click on the work "Breakdown Structure" in the top of the center panel to access the whole process.

If you experience any problem, have any suggestion or questions please report to Ildevana Poltronieri - ildevana@gmail.com or WhatsApp (51) 995915647.

Now that you know the Usa-DSL Process, could you please answer to our Survey at Link: <http://tiny.cc/tmawoz>

Thank you for helping us.